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THE EFFECT OF PRAGMATIC INSTRUCTION ON EFL LEARNERS' AWARENESS OF SUGGESTIONS

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Abstract

This study examined the effect of pragmatic instruction on the awareness of suggestions of Persian Efl learners. 34 Persian Efl learners of English took part in this study, 16 of whom received 10 sessions of awareness-raising instruction on the main head acts and downgraders in suggestions as the experimental group and the rest served as the control group with no instruction on the main head acts and downgraders. All the participants engaged in rating assessment tests before and after the study. The results indicated that the experimental group receiving pragmatic instruction outperformed the control group in awareness of appropriate and accurate suggestions. It became evident that explicit instruction on pragmatic aspects of L2 to foreign language learners could aid both learners and teachers in developing learners' pragmatic competence. The findings of this study imply that integrating specific instructional treatments in foreign language classroom may raise learners' pragmatic awareness in the target language.

Key words: pragmatics, awareness-raising instruction, suggestions, Efl students

1. Introduction

Learners of all languages, as observations show, tend to have difficulty understanding the intended meaning communicated by a speech act, or producing a speech act using appropriate language and manner in the language being learned. Second or foreign language learners (SLL/ FLL) show significant differences from native speakers in language use, the execution and comprehension of certain speech acts, conversational functions such as greetings, and conversational management such as of back channeling and short responses (see, for example, Bardovi-Harlig, 1999, 2001; Kasper and Schmidt, 1996; Kasper and Rose, 1999).

Speech act behavior has been a central concern for researchers in the field of interlanguage pragmatics in which a major focus of study is the pragmatic difficulties that distinguish the behavior of second language (L2) learners from that of target language speakers (Yu, 2004, p. 102). Although successfully learning a new language does not mean that learners, when employing the L2, have to forego their native language (L1) norms completely and adopt the culture of that new language, the differences in the behaviors of L1 and L2 speakers have engaged researchers in interlanguage pragmatics. Lack of mastery of grammar, combined with sociolinguistic confusion, can make learners appear improper or incompetent. It can also cause misunderstandings or create offense when learners can understand only the literal meaning of words and do not know the rules of use for interpreting those words (Rintell &

Mitchell, 1989). Such differences often contribute to unexpected pragmatic failure and possibly to serious trouble for L2 learners.

2. Review of literature

Research has found that classroom instruction on speech acts can help learners improve their performance of speech acts and thus their interactions with native speakers. Without instruction, differences in pragmatics show up in the English of learners regardless of their first language background or language proficiency. Bardovi-Harlig (2001) points out that advanced nonnative speakers are neither uniformly successful nor uniformly unsuccessful with respect to pragmatic aspects of L2, but the range is quite wide.

What seems to be of significance with respect to pragmatic differences is that, unlike the case of grammatical errors, they are often interpreted on a social or personal level rather than as a result of language learning process. Left on their own devices, i.e. previous knowledge and universal pragmatic properties, with respect to contact with the target language in and out of the classroom, the majority of learners apparently do not acquire the pragmatics of the target language on their own (Bardovi-Harlig, 2001; Kasper, 2001). Drawing on studies on interlanguage pragmatics (ILPs), it seems that the chief goal of instruction in pragmatics is to raise learners' pragmatic awareness and give them choices about their interaction in the target language. Interlanguage pragmatics is defined by Kasper (cited in Dogancay-aktuna and Kamisli, 1997) as " the branch of second language acquisition research which studies how non-native speakers (NNS) understand and carry out linguistic action in the target language, and how they acquire second language pragmatic knowledge (p. 3). Thus, as claimed by Ellis (1985), interlanguage entails knowledge of language, which is different from both the learner's mother tongue and the target language (TL) system they are trying to acquire.

Bardovi-Harlig (2001) makes a strong case for the necessity of instruction providing evidence that the learners differ noticeably from native speakers in their production and perception of the speech acts in the target language. The need for examining the effects of instruction in pragmatics is further documented by Schmidt's (1993) contention that simple exposure to the target language is insufficient - pragmatic functions and relevant contextual factors are often not salient to the learner and so not likely to be noticed even after prolonged exposure. In addition, research has revealed that noticing a form is the key to beginning the cognitive processes that result in L2 acquisition (Leow, 1997).

To address the need for instructional intervention in interlanguage pragmatics (Bardovi-Harlig, 2001), there has been a considerable increase in the number and range of studies on instructed ILPs (see Kasper, 2001; Kasper and Rose, 2002; Rose and Kasper, 2001).

Rose (2002) distinguishes three groups of ILP studies, i. e. teachability studies (whether a particular area of pragmatics is at all teachable), instruction versus exposure (whether instruction is better than exposure), and different pedagogical approaches (whether explicit or implicit). The first group of studies have examined the teachability of various pragmatic features including conversational implicature (Safont, 2003; Salazar, 2003), interactional norms (Liddicoat and Crozet, 2001), apologies (Olshtain and Cohen, 1990).

The studies dealing with instruction versus exposure simply tried to determine whether instruction in the target feature is more effective than no instruction (Billmyer, 1990; Bouton, 1994; Lyster, 1994; Yoshimi, 2001). The third group of ILP studies compared the effectiveness of different pedagogical approaches, i. e. explicit versus implicit (Kubota, 1995; House, 1996; Tateyama, 2001; Rose and Ng, 2001; Takahashi, 2001; Fukuya et al., 1998; Fukuya and Clark,

2001; Martinez-Flor and Fukuya, 2005). Instruction versus exposure studies represented a wide range of learning targets. Bouton (1994) selected the understanding of implicature as his learning target, while Lyster (1994) examined the use of French *tu/ vous* in informal and formal contexts.

Following the second group of ILPs studies, the present study aims to investigate whether or not pragmatic instruction can lead to an improvement in learners' perception, i. e. awareness, regarding the speech act of suggestion.

Empirical studies dealing with pragmatic transfer have found that learners transfer the linguistic forms for making speech acts in general from their mother tongue to English. The speech act of suggesting is no exception. Developing learners' ability to comprehend and use this particular speech act in the TL would contribute to learners' overall communicative competence. Suggestions belong to the group of directive speech acts. According to Searle (1976), directives are speech acts in which the speaker's purpose is to get the hearer to commit himself to some future course of action. In his view, directives are attempts to make the world match the words. One relevant feature affecting directives in opposition to other speech acts refers to the necessary interaction between the speaker and the hearer in order to have the speech act realized (Searle, 1976).

Compared with other speech acts specifically requests, the speech act of suggestion is not a widely investigated one as far as one is concerned with pragmatic instruction. However, several interlanguage studies have focused on suggestions. The study conducted by Bardovi-Harlig and Hartford in 1990 was the first one to address suggestions from a developmental perspective. In fact, Bardovi-Harlig and Hartford (1990) were interested in examining authentic conversations between advisors and students in order to pay attention to the status congruence between both parties, that is to say, whether the linguistic forms employed by the two interlocutors were congruent with their respective status. By comparing the linguistic negotiation of status between NSs and non-native speakers (NNSs), these authors concluded that they differed in their pragmatic competence, since NNSs, although highly competent linguistically, did not have the ability to employ the status-preserving strategies in accordance with their status.

Bardovi-Harlig and Hartford (1990) focused on interaction between advisors and students in order to examine whether the linguistic forms used by the interlocutors were congruent with their status or they were noncongruent and as a result, status played no role in the congruence between the interlocutors. Congruence is defined by Bardovi-Harlig and Hartford (1990) as, "the match of the speaker's status and the appropriateness of the speech acts given that status" (p. 473). The results of the study indicated that native speakers and nonnative speakers differed in their pragmatic competence. They relate the results to the fact that linguistically competent nonnative speakers lack the ability to employ the status-preserving strategies in accordance with their status.

Taking Bardovi-Harlig and Hartford's (1990) study into account, Alcón (2001, cited in Martinez-Flor, 2005) developed a cross-sectional investigation examining suggestions within the framework of status congruence in an ESL setting. Alcón chose 15 Spanish students and tape 30 sessions of using suggestions and analyzed them considering both their frequency and form. Results of this study showed that, in spite of receiving positive input from teachers, students' percentage of direct forms and the absence of mitigators revealed the lack of pragmatic competence.

In addition to abovementioned interlanguage pragmatic studies, Matsumura conducted two other studies within this area in ESL and EFL contexts. In the first study which was a longitudinal one, Matsumura (2001) compared Japanese ESL and EFL learners' degrees of change that came about over time in perception of social status in advice acts. The results of this study indicated that living and studying in an ESL setting results in the students' pragmatic competence development. Due particularly to the exposition to the authentic target forms of advice; Japanese ESL learners outperformed the EFL group in perceiving social status in advice acts.

Next, among studies dealing with the speech act of suggestion is the one conducted by Martinez-Flor and Fukuya (2005). Martinez-Flor and Fukuya (2005) examined the effects of explicit and implicit instruction on the Spanish learners' production of pragmatically appropriate and linguistically accurate suggestions. For this purpose, 81 intermediate Spanish learners of English were divided into three groups of explicit, implicit, and control. The explicit group was provided with metapragmatic information on the main head acts of the speech act of suggestion. The students' awareness in the implicit group was raised by the use of different activities and tasks. The results of this study indicated that, in comparison to the control group, both the explicit and the implicit groups improved their pragmatic competence considering their production, awareness, and confidence when judging the appropriateness of suggestions.

In the second study, Matsumura (2003) examined learners' pragmatic development on the basis of their approximation to NSs' preferences for advice type depending on different social status. Results of this study indicated that the amount of exposure to the target forms affected learners' pragmatic development to a high degree compared with the level of proficiency.

Because of a widely held attitude among the textbook writers and curriculum developers concerning learning pragmatic formation through contact with the target language and culture over time rather than through instruction, this study addresses the use of instruction, implementing a focus on FormS methodology, to lead learners to notice pragmatic forms and subsequently to produce appropriate and accurate suggestions in a foreign language classroom context. To address the above concerns, the following research question is investigated in this study:

1. Does pragmatic instruction affect Iranian EFL Learners' awareness of appropriate and accurate suggestions?

3. Methodology

3.1. Participants

The participants taking part in this study were 34 Persian learners of English (all males). They had studied English for four years with only one of them who stated that he had been to an English speaking country. A test of English proficiency (TOEFL) showed that all the participants had an intermediate level of English language proficiency. The students were randomly assigned to an experimental group (N= 16) and a control group (N= 18). The average age was 18.4 years for the experimental group and 18.7 years for the control group.

3.2. Target Forms

Following Martinez-Flor and Fukuya (2005), the researcher focused on 12 head acts (HAs) to perform suggestions and seven downgraders to soften the force of this speech act. These

target forms were selected, according to these authors, considering (a) universal pragmatic strategies for speech acts (Kasper and Schmidt, 1996), (b) a politeness theory (Brown and Levinson, 1987), (c) previous ILP studies focusing on suggestions (Hinkel, 1994, 1997; Matsumura, 2001, 2003), and (d) native speakers' oral and written production data. Based on the sociopragmatic factor of status (Brown and Levinson, 1987), these target forms were classified into (1) equal status (equal academic status between a speaker and an interlocutor) and, (2) higher status (higher academic status of an interlocutor than that of the speaker). Table 1 below illustrates the taxonomy of suggestion linguistic realization strategies.

Table 1. Taxonomies of suggestion linguistic realization strategies (adopted from Martinez-Flor, 2005, p. 175)

TYPE	STRATEGY	LINGUISTIC FORMS
DIRECT	(1) Performative Verb	I suggest that you I advise you to I recommend that you
	Noun of suggestion	My suggestion (to you) would be / is...
	Imperative	Try using ...
	Negative imperative	Don't try to ... Why don't you...?
CONVENTIONALIZED FORMS	(5) Specific formulae (interrogative forms)	How about ...?
		What about ...?
		Have you thought about ...?
		You can ...
	Possibility/probability	You could ...
		You may ...
		You might ...
	Should Need	You should ...
You need to ...		
Indirect	Conditional Impersonal	If I were you, I would ...
		One thing (that you can do) would be ... Here's one possibility ... There are a number of options that you ... It would be helpful if you ...
	Hints	It might be better to ... A good idea would be ... It would be nice if ... I've heard that ...

3.3. *Instruction*

Over a three-week period, the participants in the experimental group received ten sessions of 2-hour instruction on the use of suggestions in the English. Instruction for the experimental group embodied the focus on FormS approach which is characterized by explicitness and deduction and included the provision of explanation on the use of the main head acts and downgraders which constituted the instructional foci of the study. The control group, taught by a second instructor who was regularly observed, received no identical instruction on suggestions in particular and pragmatics in general. The control group students were studying a general course of English in their syllabus. The experimental group students were exposed to several transcribed situations in which a native speaker of English made a suggestion to another person during oral interaction about computer. Then, the students took part in a series of awareness-raising (i. e. reading tasks on themes in the transcriptions). In the meantime, they received not only explicit instruction on the grammatical accuracy of the target forms, but also metapragmatic information about the appropriate use of the target forms.

3.4. *Instruments*

The data for this study are composed of the experimental and control groups' performances on a rating assessment test. The four situations in the rating assessment pre- and post-tests were distinct in terms of content and themes in order to avoid practice effect.

The rating assessment pre- and post-tests were administered before the and after treatment. The rating assessment test required the students to rate the appropriateness of suggestions made in each situation on a 5-point rating scale (1= inappropriate; 5= appropriate). The tests were constructed in such a way as to offer two appropriate situations and two inappropriate situations. The rating assessment pre- and post-tests were adopted from Martinez-Flor and Fykuya (2005) and are provided in appendix at the end of the paper.

3.5. *Data analysis*

The correct ratings in rating assessment pre- and post-tests for both the experimental and control groups were counted and then compared to determine the degree of improvement. In order to classify these data, the taxonomies for both head acts and downgraders adopted from previous research on the speech act under study (Fukuya and Zhang, 2002; Martinez-Flor and Fukuya, 2005) served as analytical tools.

4. **Results**

Before examining the hypothesis related to the research question, it is important to point out that all the HAs and downgraders from the production data were categorized. In this way, Tables 1 and 2 present, on the one hand, the frequency and percentage of the target forms and, on the other hand, the non-target forms that include the rest of the categorized realizations for both HAs and downgraders, respectively.

Table 1. Frequency and percentage of the suggestions (HAs) categorized as the target and non- target forms used by the two groups in both the pre-test and post-test

	Experimental (n=16)				Control (n=18)			
	Pre-test		Post-test		Pre-test		Post-test	
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%
<i>HAs in target forms</i>	15	23.4	61	95.3	24	33.4	10	13.9

<i>HAs in non-target forms</i>	49	76.6	3	4.3	48	66.6	62	86.1
TOTAL	64	100.0	64	100.0	72	100.0	72	100.0

Note. n = number of forms

Table 2. Frequency and percentage of the downgraders categorized as the corresponding target and non-target forms used by the two groups in both the pre-test and post-test

	Explicit (n=24)				Control (n=32)			
	Pre-test		Post-test		Pre-test		Post-test	
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%
<i>Downgraders as target forms</i>	2	3.1	46	71.9	8	11.2	1	1.4
<i>Downgraders in non-target forms</i>	62	96.9	18	28.1	64	88.8	71	98.6
TOTAL	64	100.0	64	100.0	72	100.	72	100.0

Note. n = number of forms

Results from rating assessment test

In order to examine the effects of instruction on pragmatic awareness of the participants, the two groups' ratings were compared. The result of Chi-square conducted (Table 3) on the participants ratings of pragmatic appropriateness in the pre-test revealed that the two groups were not significantly different ($\chi^2=0.69$).

Table 3: Chi-square results for Awareness in the Pretest

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	.698(a)	4	.952
Likelihood Ratio	.698	4	.952
Linear-by-Linear Association	.069	1	.793
N of Valid Cases	136		

* Sig. at p<0.05 level

In the post-test, however, the results of a Chi-square (Table 4) indicated an overall effect of pragmatic instruction on experimental group's awareness of appropriate and accurate suggestions.

Table 4: Chi-square results for Awareness in the Posttest

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	23.363(a)	4	.000
Likelihood Ratio	24.142	4	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	.059	1	.807
N of Valid Cases	136		

* Sig. at p<0.05 level

5. Discussion

The findings, thus, seem to prove the effectiveness of instruction, since the treatment group significantly improved its awareness of pragmatically appropriate suggestions in the post-

test as compared to the pre-test. This result is in line with previous research that has also focused on the effects of instruction on the production and awareness of a particular speech act (Billmyer, 1990; Olshtain and Cohen, 1990; Martinez-Flor and Fukuya, 2005). Therefore, it may be claimed that the present study widens the learning targets by focusing on suggestions as a pragmatic learning feature that might be teachable in the classroom setting, and specifically in the FL classroom through a focus on FormS mediation in the form of awareness-raising activities.

The findings seem to indicate that the instruction implemented in the present study was effective in enhancing participants' awareness of and sensitivity to the speech act of suggestion in different situations. These findings are in line with previous research that has proved the efficacy of instruction to develop learners' ability to comprehend different pragmatic aspects (Kubota, 1995, cited in Rose, 2005; Martinez-Flor and Fukuya, 2005). After a period of instruction, the experimental learners in Kubota's (1995) study significantly improved their capacity to interpret implicature appropriately when compared to the control group. Similarly, the instructional group in the present study also significantly outperformed the control group in their awareness of appropriate suggestions.

Moreover, the results also seem to support Martinez-Flor and Fukuya's (2005) study on suggestions in which, although being mainly designed to address the effects of two types of instruction, i. e. *Explicit and implicit*, on learners' production of this particular speech act, the authors also examined whether training EFL learners in the use of suggestions would influence their pragmatic awareness. Results from this study were statistically significant in learners' identification of appropriate and inappropriate suggestion forms.

6. Conclusion

The primary purpose of the present study was to examine the relative effects of explicit pragmatic instruction on awareness of appropriate and accurate suggestions. This study can be considered to be of practical use especially in a foreign language context where learning English pragmatics in addition to English grammar has become one of the most significant areas of focus, and where exposure to English is limited and where only limited class time is available for teaching English.

The results of the present study indicate that explicit pragmatic instruction in form of consciousness-raising tasks can work when they provide an emphasis on forms and meanings. In this respect, teachers may need to examine the kinds of task they use in their English lessons to see to what extent they provide learners with the opportunity for processing both the forms and meanings of the target features.

The present study suggests that there are several limitations that future research needs to consider. Regarding the mode of testing, it seems essential to add an on-line test in order to measure automatic processing skills. The test should be a timed test, to allow for semantic processing and noticing, but not for conscious reflection.

The present study has demonstrated how a specific type of instruction (i.e. explicit) was operationalised and implemented to promote learners' pragmatic competence in the classroom context. Here, the role of learning strategies and styles may be of significance, an issue which should be further researched.

References

- Bardovi-Harlig, K. (1999). Exploring the Interlanguage of Interlanguage Pragmatics: A Research Agenda for Acquisitional Pragmatics. *Language Learning*, 49(4), 677-713.
- Bardovi-Harlig, K. (2001). Empirical evidence of the need for instruction in pragmatics. In K. R. Rose, & G. Kasper (Eds.) *Pragmatics in language teaching* (pp. 13-32). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Bardovi-Harlig, K., & Hartford, B. S. (1990). Congruence in native and nonnative conversations: Status balance in the academic advising session. *Language Learning*, 40, 467-501.
- Billmyer, K. (1990). I really like your lifestyle: ESL learners learning how to compliment. *Penn Working Papers in Educational Linguistics*, 6(2), 31-48.
- Bouton, L. F. (1994). Can NNS skill in interpreting implicature in American English be improved through explicit instruction? - A pilot study. In L. F. Bouton, & Y. Kachru (Eds.) *Pragmatics and language learning*, 5. Urbana, IL, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign. pp. 88-109.
- Dogaci-Aktuna, s., & Kamisli, S. (1997). *Pragmatic Transfer in Interlanguage Development: A Case Study of Advanced EFL learners*. Paper to be presented at the National Linguistic Conference (11th, Ankara, Turkey).
- Ellis, R. (1985). *Understanding second language acquisition*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Fukuya, Y., & Clark, M. (2001). A comparison of input enhancement and explicit instruction of mitigators. In L. Bouton (Ed.) *Pragmatics and language learning*, vol. 10 (pp. 111-130.). Urbana, IL: University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign.
- Fukuya, Y., Reeve, M., Gisi, J., & Christianson, M. (1998). *Does focus on form work for sociopragmatics?* Paper presented at the 12th Annual International on Pragmatics and Language Learning. Urbana, IL: University of Illinois at Urbana-Conference Champaign.
- Fukuya, Y., & Zhang, Y. (2002). Effects of recasts on EFL learners' acquisition of pragmalinguistic conventions of requests. *Second Language Studies*, 21(1), *Working Papers of the Department of Second Language Studies, University of Hawaii*. 1- 47.
- Hinkel, E. (1994). Appropriateness of Advice as L2 solidarity strategy. *RELJ Journal*, 25(1), 71-93.
- Hinkel, E. (1997). Appropriateness of Advice: DCT and Multiple Choice Data. *Applied Linguistics*, 18(1), 1-26.
- House, J. (1996). Developing pragmatic fluency in English as a Foreign Language: Routines and metapragmatic awareness. *Studies in Second Language Acquisition*, 18(2), 225-252.
- Kasper, G. (2001). Classroom Research on Interlanguage Pragmatics. In K. R. Rose, & G. Kasper (Eds.) *Pragmatics in language teaching*, (pp. 33-60). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Kasper, G., & Rose, K. R. (1999). Pragmatics and SLA. *Annual Review of Applied Linguistics*, 19, 81-104.
- Kasper, G., & Rose, K. R. (2002). Pragmatic Development in a Second Language. *Language Learning*, 52: Supplement 1.
- Kasper, G., & Schmidt, R. (1996). Developmental issues in interlanguage pragmatics. *Studies on Second Language Acquisition*, 18(1), 149-169.
- Kubota, M. (1995). Teachability of conversational implicature to Japanese EFL learners. *IRLT Bulletin*, 9 (pp. 35-67.). Tokyo: Institute for Research in Language Teaching.
- Leow, R. (1997). The effects of input enhancement and text length on adult L2 readers

- comprehension and intake in second language acquisition. *Applied Language Learning*, 8, 151-182.
- Liddicoat, A. J., & Crozet, C. (2001). Acquiring French interactional norms through instruction. In K. R. Rose, & G. Kasper (Eds.) *Pragmatics in language teaching* (pp. 125-144). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Lyster, R. (1994). The effect of functional-analytical teaching on aspects of French immersion students' sociolinguistic competence. *Applied Linguistics*, 15(3), 263-287.
- Martinez-Flor, A., & Fukuya, J. Y. (2005). The effects of instruction on learners' production of appropriate and accurate suggestions. *System*, 33(3), 463-480.
- Martinez-Flor, A. (2005). A Theoretical Review of the Speech Act of Suggesting: Towards a Taxonomy for its Use in FLT. *Revista Alicantina Estudios Ingleses*, 18, 167-187
- Matsumura, S. (2001). Learning the rules for offering advice: A quantitative approach to second language socialization. *Language Learning*, 51(4), 635-679.
- Matsumura, S. (2003). Modeling the relationships among interlanguage pragmatic development, L2 proficiency, and exposure to L2. *Applied Linguistics*, 24(4) 465-491.
- Olshain, E., & Cohen, A. D. (1990). The learning of complex speech act behavior. *TESL Canada Journal*, 7(1), 45-65.
- Rintell, E., & Mitchell, C. J. (1989). Studying requests and apologies: An inquiry into method. In S. Blum-Kulka, J. House, & G. Kasper (Eds.), *Cross-cultural pragmatics: Requests and apologies* (pp. 248-273). Norwood, NJ: Ablex.
- Rose, K. R. (2000). An exploratory cross-sectional study of interlanguage pragmatic development. *Studies in Second Language Acquisition*, 22, 27-67.
- Rose, K. R. and Kasper, G. (2001) (Eds.). *Pragmatics in language teaching*. Cambridge Cambridge University Press.
- Rose, K. R. and Ng Kwai-fun, C. (2001). Inductive and deductive approaches to teaching compliments and compliment responses. In K. R. Rose, & G. Kasper (Eds.) *Pragmatics in language teaching* (pp. 145-170). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Safont, P. (2003). Instructional effects on the use of request acts modification devices by EFL learners. In A. Martinez-Flor, E. Usó, & A. Fernández (Eds.) *Pragmatic competence in foreign language teaching*, (pp. 211-232). Castelli: Servei de Publicacions de la Universitat Jaume I.
- Salazar, P. (2003). Pragmatic instruction in the EFL context. In A. Martinez-Flor, E. Usó, & A. Fernández (Eds.) *Pragmatic competence in foreign language teaching*, (pp. 233-246). Castelli: Servei de Publicacions de la Universitat Jaume I.
- Schmidt, R. (1993). Consciousness, learning and Interlanguage pragmatics. In G. Kasper, & S. Blum-Kulka (Eds.) *Interlanguage pragmatics* (pp. 21-42). New York: Oxford University Press.
- Searle, J. R. (1976). The classification of illocutionary acts. *Language in Society*, 5(1), 1-24.
- Takahashi, S. (2001). The role of input enhancement in developing pragmatic competence. In K. R. Rose, & G. Kasper (Eds.) *Pragmatics in language teaching* (pp. 171-199). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Tateyama, Y. (2001). Explicit and implicit teaching of pragmatic routines. In K. R. Rose, & G. Kasper (Eds.) *Pragmatics in language teaching*, (pp. 200-222). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Yoshimi, D. R. (2001). Explicit instruction and the use of interactional discourse markers. In K. R. Rose, & G. Kasper (Eds.) *Pragmatics in language teaching*, pp. 223-244). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

Yu, M. (2004). Interlinguistic variation and similarity in second language speech act behavior. *The Modern Language Journal*, 88(1), 102-119.

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